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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A Visual Identify Guide (VIG) has been created to simplify the identification and the understanding of the mission and value of the Beaconing Project. The specific public identity will be reflected on all the dissemination content produced by the project both printed and online materials. Beaconing's VIG provides guidance and specific instructions for the coherent and cohesive implementation of the project visual identity and graphic elements in all forms of communication used in the project. Subsequent sections of this deliverable provide details on the proper use of the Beaconing logos, typography, iconography, and colour.

The Beaconing website is one of the key elements for the dissemination and identity of the project. It integrates public and private sections that support both internal and external communication, and stimulate collaboration through gamified mechanisms. Coupled with social media presence, the website is critical in attracting, retaining, and engaging support from Beaconing's key audiences. The Beaconing website was constructed following web accessibility guides and designed to accommodate various types of audiences. This document also describes what the Key Performance Indicators are for the Beaconing website and social media presence.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

This report details the outcomes of the project branding and online presence activities, which, as stated in the DoA, aim to provide a cohesive visual identity for the project and online dissemination channels, enabling consortium members to communicate efficiently and congruously with key audiences. The goal of the project branding strategy is to reflect the mission and the objectives of the Beaconing Project in a clear, consistent, and cohesive manner, providing partners with visual and editorial tools that enable them to articulate and express in different languages an authentic representation of the project objectives and outcomes.

1.2 ROLE OF THIS DELIVERABLE IN THE PROJECT

This deliverable presents the Visual Identity Guidelines (VIG), the main sections and functionalities of the project website and the key Communication/ Promotion Materials that underpin the distinctiveness of the project and construct sustainable mechanisms to support dissemination activities during and beyond the life of the project.

The objective of the VIG is to provide a unified, meaningful project *brand* that complies with the quality, and the innovative impact of Beaconing. The Communication/Promotion Materials were constructed in accordance with these VIG.

The Beaconing website is one of the key elements for the dissemination and identity of the project. At consortium level, the private section of the project website aims to enhance internal communication among partners through wiki and discussion pages, scheduling of events, as well as uploads of project deliverables.

The public sections of the website coupled with a strong presence in well-established social media channels, provides partners with mechanisms that increase the visibility, the impact of the project outcomes, and consolidate the project brand.

1.3 APPROACH

The visual identity of the Beaconing project and the structure of the website have been defined and developed based on the information and requirements collected from the project coordinator and the partners during face-to-face meetings and via email conversations. In addition, we have collaborated with European and national projects, building upon past experiences.

1.4 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The deliverable includes the following sections:

- Section 2 defines the key visual identity elements of the Beaconing Project, as well as the project website guidelines, restrictions, and accessibility criteria;
- Section 3 details the characteristics and options available in the public and private sections of the Beaconing website;
- Section 4 provides insights on the social media accounts that have been created to promote the Beaconing Project;

- Section 5 presents the gamification mechanisms that have been integrated into the Beaconing website;
- Section 6 presents the outcomes of the project online presence via the website and social media based on the impact objectives included in the DoA.

2 PROJECT BRANDING

The look-and-feel of the Beaconing Visual Identity, including the master brand, colour palette, typography and graphic style, are explained in the following guidelines of the VIG. The guidelines have been developed through careful consideration of many factors, both functional and aesthetic, and adhering to them will ensure a clear and consistent graphic identity. The Beaconing Visual Identity may not be used in any manner that suggests or implies the project is endorsing political parties or views, or religious organizations or beliefs. The Beaconing Visual Identity must be used on all the print-and screen-based applications (including publications, promotional materials, PowerPoint presentations, Web sites, conference and event materials, advertising, plaques, certificates, etc.) that are large enough to allow the Beaconing Logo to appear at least at its minimum size. All the versions of the Logo can be downloaded from the public website at <http://Beaconing.eu/download/>

2.1 BEACONING LOGO

The Beaconing logo is a combination of the project acronym and the symbol which represents in a graphic style a beacon. The inclusion of this symbol in the logo reflects the core idea of the project, where students will be able to learn and collaborate in a blended environment that employs beacon technology.

The wordmark of the Beaconing logo uses the typeface **Diana Sans**. The spacing between the letters has been adjusted for maximum effect and should not be altered. For that reason, do not attempt to re-create the wordmark. Rather, always download the full logo available online at www.Beaconing.eu. Admissible variations of the logo are shown on the following pages. All the slightly different versions are clearly identified as representation of the same project.

The Beaconing Logo is available in three versions:

Figure 1. Dark wordmark

Dark wordmark colour and transparent background. This is the main logo of the Beaconing Project.

Figure 2. White wordmark

White wordmark colour and transparent background. (To explain the use of the logo we used a black dotted background to show this version of the logo).

Figure 3. Coloured symbol version

Coloured symbol version. This logo can be used as an alternative to the main logo in flyers, posters, brochures, etc.

2.2 BEACONING VISUAL IDENTITY GUIDELINES

The Beaconing Symbol was created to reflect the project philosophy and promote immediate identification by the public. The symbol represents a stylised version of a **beacon** and can be

used as a substitute for the Beaconing logo when space is limited. Like the main Beaconing Logo, the symbol consists of three versions:

Figure 4. Beaconing symbol

2.3 PRINTING ON COLOUR BACKGROUNDS

Figure 5. Logo printed on light backgrounds

Printing on Light Backgrounds

When printing the logo on light backgrounds, use the Dark wordmark colour (Figure 5).

Figure 6. Logo printed on dark backgrounds

Printing on Dark Backgrounds

When printing the logo on dark backgrounds, use the White wordmark colour (Figure 6).

2.4 REPRODUCTION IN ONE COLOR

The logo and the symbol can be inverted in black or white versions, although it is recommended to use the original examples. Reproducing the Symbol in Black and White Screen values may be adjusted for various printing techniques to maintain tonal differentiation.

Figure 7. Logo black version

Black version

Can be used on light backgrounds

Figure 8. Logo white version

White version

Can be used on dark version

2.5 SIZE AND CLEAR SPACE

The Beaconing Logo should be integrated in various materials at a reasonable size to maintain legibility. On printed materials, the recommended width of Beaconing logo, *whenever it is possible*, should not be smaller than 5 cm, with a height no smaller than 1 cm. The light blue area in the diagrams indicates the amount of space that must be maintained between the logo

and any other element, including the edge of a page. The clear space requirement is intended to prevent the logo from being crowded by other typographic or graphic elements. Minimum standards are described on the pictures below:

Figure 9. Clear space requirement for the logo

When using the Beaconing Symbol, whenever it is possible, its width should not be smaller than 2cm, with a height no smaller than 2.45 cm. The clear space requirement is intended to prevent the symbol from being crowded by other typographic or graphic elements.

Figure 10. Clear space requirement for symbol

2.6 INCORRECT USAGE

The Beaconing logo has been created based on a typeface and it has been customized and handset, so any alteration of the wordmark is prohibited.

For maximum impact and overall consistency, it is important to protect the integrity of the Beaconing logo. Always reproduce the logo from original artwork and avoid the improper colour usage illustrated here. These examples apply to all logo varieties.

Figure 11. Incorrect usage of Beaconing logo

Please also take into account the following rules when using the Beaconing logo:

- Do not use any other typeface to spell out Beaconing;
- Do not substitute the wordmark with other text;
- The size and arrangements of the elements should not be changed;
- Do not combine the wordmark with other symbols;
- Do not use the symbol as a substitute in copy;
- Do not alter the colours of the logo. You can only invert the logo in black or white colour, or use the additional samples;
- Do not obscure or hide parts of the logo;
- Do not place any text within the minimum clear space, explained in section **Size and clear space**.

2.7 COLOR USAGE

2.7.1 Main colours

The colours that have been used for the Beaconing Project creates powerful visual impact proving a signal of quality. We encourage the use of the following colours whenever possible. The official colours of the Beaconing Project are: **Burnt Orange** (#FF6C3A) and **Bunker** (#222935). These colours are the main colours of the logo.

Burnt Orange (#FF6C3A)

In a RGB colour space, hex #ff6c3a is composed of 100% red, 42.4% green and 22.7% blue. Whereas in a CMYK colour space, it is composed of 0% cyan, 57.6% magenta, 77.3% yellow and 0% black. It has a hue angle of 15.2 degrees, a saturation of 100% and a lightness of 61.4%.

Bunker (#222935)

In a RGB colour space, hex #222935 is composed of 13.3% red, 16.1% green and 20.8% blue. Whereas in a CMYK colour space, it is composed of 35.8% cyan, 22.6% magenta, 0% yellow and 79.2% black. It has a hue angle of 217.9 degrees, a saturation of 21.8% and a lightness of 17.1%

2.7.2 Additional colours

A set of colors complementary to the main colors has been defined to support the design of congruent promotional materials and consolidate the visual identity of the project.

Pilandros (#DD3300)

In a RGB color space, hex #dd3300 is composed of 86.7% red, 20% green and 0% blue. Whereas in a CMYK color space, it is composed of 0% cyan, 76.9% magenta, 100% yellow and 13.3% black. It has a hue angle of 13.8 degrees, a saturation of 100% and a lightness of 43.3%.

Pacific Blue (#1795C5)

In a RGB color space, hex #1795c5 is composed of 9% red, 58.4% green and 77.3% blue. Whereas in a CMYK color space, it is composed of 88.3% cyan, 24.4% magenta, 0% yellow and 22.7% black. It has a hue angle of 196.6 degrees, a saturation of 79.1% and a lightness of 43.1%.

Supernova (#FDBE3D)

In a RGB colour space, hex #fdb3d is composed of 99.2% red, 74.5% green and 23.9% blue. Whereas in a CMYK colour space, it is composed of 0% cyan, 24.9% magenta, 75.9% yellow and 0.8% black. It has a hue angle of 40.3 degrees, a saturation of 98% and a lightness of 61.6%.

2.8 TYPOGRAPHY

The role of the Beaconing typography is to strengthen the visual identity of the project across the dissemination efforts. The Typeface has unique characteristics that help communicate specific messages and can work together with other design elements to make communications more readable, consistent and visually appealing. The official typeface of the Beaconing Project is **Diana Sans**, typed on lowercase, which was chosen for its modern styling to give the logo a unique identity.

The use of the font is not mandatory. For internal documents the font **Calibri** has been proposed as an alternative.

OFFICIAL TYPEFACE – DIANA SANS

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

ALTERNATIVE TYPEFACE - CALIBRI

2.9 ICONOGRAPHY

The following icons created for the Beaconing Project provides an efficient way to remember specific content in the website and other applications.

Figure 12. Iconography

2.10 SAMPLES OF STATIONARY APPLICATIONS

A set of templates has been created and made available to the Beaconing consortium to enable a consistent communication with the Beaconing stakeholders. The templates are not mandatory, serve as guidelines, and aim to harmonize the implementation efforts.

Letterhead

Beaconing letterhead is to be used by all the partners of the project. The suggested format for the letter is described in the body of the sample letter. The format of the letterhead is just a suggestion. It is required to include in the Letterhead the Logo, the Footer and the Contact information.

Stationery

Format
21,59 x 27,94 cm

Logo Size
6,8 cm

Sender Header
Font: Calibri, 10pt
Color: rgb 89, 89, 89

Date
Font: Calibri, 10pt, Bold,
Color: rgb 255, 108, 58

Paragraph: before 18pt, after 18pt, Line Multiple 1,2pt

Recipient Header
Font: Calibri, 10pt
Color: rgb 89, 89, 89

Paragraph: before 2pt, after 2pt, Line Multiple 1,2pt

Content
Font: Calibri, 10pt
Color: rgb 89, 89, 89

Paragraph: before 2pt, after 2pt, Line Multiple 1,2pt

Closing content
Font: Calibri, 10pt
Color: rgb 89, 89, 89

Paragraph: before 24pt, after 48pt, Line Multiple 1,2pt

Figure 13. Beaconing letterhead sample

Envelope

Beaconing Envelope is to be used by all the partners of the project. The suggested format for envelope is described in the body of the sample. The format of the envelope is just a suggestion. It is required to include in the Envelope the Logo and the Contact information.

Stationery

Format
24,13 x 10,48 cm

Logo Size
6,8 cm

Sender Header

Font: Calibri, 10pt
Color: rgb 255, 108, 58, rgb 89, 89, 89
Paragraph: before 6pt, after 0pt, Line Multiple 1,2pt

Recipient Header

Font: Calibri, 10pt, Bold
Color: rgb 89, 89, 89
Paragraph: before 6pt, after 0pt, Line Multiple 1,2pt

Figure 14. Beaconing Envelope sample

Fax

Stationery

Format
21,59 x 27,94 cm

Logo Size
6,8 cm

Title

Font: Calibri, 74pt
Color: rgb 255, 108, 58
Paragraph: before 12pt, after 12pt, Line Multiple 1,2pt

Content

Font: Calibri, 10pt
Color: rgb 89, 89, 89
Format: Table

Figure 15. Beaconing Fax sample

Additional Stationery Items

Flyers, PowerPoint presentations, newsletters and other materials can be downloaded from <http://Beaconing.eu/download/>.

Using the Beaconing visual identity correctly and consistently is essential to maintaining the equity. As outlined in the previous pages, consideration should be given to clear space, minimum size, size ratio, color, background, and placement.

Below are presented the format of different printed and screen-based applications.

Flyers

Figure 16. Beaconing flyer sample

POSTER

BEACONING stands for Breaking Educational Barriers with Contextualised, Pervasive and Gameful Learning and will focus on 'anytime anywhere' learning by exploiting pervasive, context-aware and gamified techniques and technologies, framed under the Problem-Based Learning approach.

GRANT AGREEMENT 687676

CONTACT DETAILS

Email: sarnab@coventry.ac.uk
Mobile: 07795 818977
<http://beaconing.eu>

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework
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BEACONING - Grant Agreement 687676

Figure 17. Beaconing poster sample

PowerPoint presentation

Figure 18. Beaconing PowerPoint template sample

Newsletter

Figure 19. Beaconing newsletter template sample

2.11 WEBSITE GUIDELINES

As previously stated the Beaconing website is one of the key elements for the dissemination and identity of the project. The website guidelines have been developed with the goal of providing a standardized identity for the Beaconing Project website. All uses of the Beaconing marks must comply with the project's VIG and should not be modified without prior approval from the project coordinator.

Logo use on the web

It is recommended to follow the visual identity standards described in this document when using the Beaconing logo on the web.

Web colour palette and secondary colour palette

All the Partners must follow correct colour specifications when using the Beaconing Project official colours (**Burnt Orange** and **Bunker**) on the web. A secondary palette of colours may be used in addition to the official colours, providing flexibility, yet protecting the integrity of the project brand.

2.12 WEB RESCTRICTIONS

The Beaconing web Visual Identity may not be used in any manner that suggests or implies the project is endorsing political parties or views, or religious organizations or beliefs.

No one other than the Beaconing consortium may claim copyright or trademark rights or seek to register any design that uses the project marks.

The Beaconing Project will not approve the use of its visual identity elements in connection with alcoholic beverages, inherently dangerous products (firearms, explosives), illegal drugs, tobacco, gambling, sexually suggestive products or language.

2.13 WEB ACCESSIBILITY

The Beaconing website adopts the web accessibility requirements and conforms to the World Wide Web Consortium's (W3C) internationally recognised Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 2.0 to the level AA (Double-A conformance). The website provides a user-friendly design and structure and can be easily navigated throughout its entire content.

The website structure was tested with two types of tools:

Mark-up Validation Service provided by W3C. The first test has returned several errors: missing language tag in head, style position error, missing alt tag for images, but the errors have been resolved. The second test returned no errors or warnings (see Appendix V).

WAVE – web accessibility evaluation tool. During the first testing phase, **11 errors**, 5 alerts and 34 contrast errors were identified. All were addressed.

Figure 20. Beaconing website accessibility first report

The second test returned 0 errors, 0 contrast error and 1 alert. The alert informs about the presence of a *noscript* tag. This element is used to show the content in case a user has JavaScript disabled on his/her device.

Figure 21. Beaconing website accessibility final report

Tests of the loading time of the project website have been carried out using Pingdom. Based on this analysis, the hosting parameters have been refined and a caching module has been implemented to achieve an overall loading time of under 2 seconds.

3 WEBSITE START-UP

The Beaconing Project website is divided into two main sections:

Public section – used for presenting project activities and progress, making public statements and announcements, as well as for online dissemination of project, deliverables, newsletters, brochures, etc.

Private section – used by consortium members who will be granted unlimited access to post information about the project, in specific sections. This part will also be used for reporting purposes and to simplify collecting information from the project partners (e.g. dissemination activities).

The **structure** of the Beaconing website is as follows:

Homepage

Insights (project): *The who; The whys; The whens; Media*

Participate (events)

Write (blog)

Download (resources)

Choose (language): *English; German; French; Italian; Spanish; Portuguese; Romanian; Polish; Turkish.*

Private section (): User statistics; Schedules; Wikis; Discussion; Deliverables. The private section will show after the login, so it visible only for the authenticated users.

Search

Figure 22 - Beaconing website structure

All the sections/pages presented above can be accessed through the **Main menu**, visible in all the pages of the website.

The main purpose of the **Login Section** is to provide the users a way to enter into the private area of the website using social networks like: Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.

3.1 BEACONING PUBLIC SECTION

3.1.1 Homepage

The Homepage aims to provide an overview of the project, including the most important information including latest news, social media activity, upcoming events, in a single web page.

At the initial stage of the website, the Homepage contains the following sections:

a. **HEADER**

- **Beaconing Top menu** with the social network **Login section**;
- **Beaconing Logo**;
- **Beaconing Main** menu composed by 7 circles (as detailed in the Figure No. 1);

- b. **MULTIMEDIA BANNER** - a video background with a brief description of the project, illustrating the main ideas of the project;

Figure 23. Header

c. **CONTENT**

The website will provide high quality content that will be updated on a regular basis as a way to attract and sustain attention from the community. The main elements from this content is:

- **Blog Section** - contains the most recent or relevant posts in the blog;
- **Fresh Section** – contain the recent tweets of the Beaconing Project Twitter account. The section will inform followers on notable project updates, publication of deliverables and events in which Beaconing consortium participate;
- **Events Section** – contain all the events at which Beaconing Project will be/has been presented and other relevant news for the Beaconing Project and a “Get involved” section dedicated to the consortium partners;
- **Multilingual Section** – contains the most recent news posted by the consortium members in their native language;

Figure 24. Content

d. FOOTER

- **EU Acknowledgement** – presents the EU flag followed by the text: “Co-funded by Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union. Beaconing Grant Agreement – 687676”;
- **Popular posts** – contains the most popular/relevant posts from the website;
- **Testimonials** – contains testimonials about the project;
- **Tags** – contains a short list of the most used tags.

Figure 25. Beaconing footer

3.1.2 Insights

The Insights page describes the overall idea of the Beaconing Project and its most important facts. The page contains the following four sub-pages:

- The who** – this page provides a list of the Beaconing Partners, their Logo, the role they have in the project, and links to their webs sites/social network for further information;
- The whys** – this page contains a more detailed description of the Beaconing Project, describing the main objectives of the project;
- The whens** – this page displays in a graphic style the Beaconing Work Packages;
- Media** – this page displays the video content of the Beaconing Project. The videos are hosted on Beaconing YouTube channel.

Figure 26. Beaconing Insights Page

3.1.3 Participate

The Participate page provides a list of the present and future events which are relevant to the Beaconing Project. The page provides a short snippet of the articles, with the possibility to access the full content. All partners can contribute to this section.

Figure 27. Beaconing Participate Page

3.1.4 Write

The Write page provides a list of the recent news. In this section the users can read, comment or vote on posts written by a member of the consortium. The main topics the Write page will focus on are related to the project activity. On each post, users can leave their comments using the provided form, can vote for the articles or share them on social networks.

Figure 28. Beaconing Write Page

3.1.5 Download

The Download page contains project resources. These resources will be uploaded to the website, and both registered and non-registered users will be able to download them.

This page contains several subsections:

- Beaconing ESSENTIALS** – users can download the Beaconing presentation;
- Beaconing PRESS RELEASE** – users can download the publications of the project;
- Beaconing LOGO** – users can download different versions of the Beaconing logo;
- Beaconing NEWSLETTER** – users can download the newsletter of the Beaconing project.

Figure 29. Beaconing Download Page

3.1.6 Choose language

The Choose Language page provides a list of the recent news articles posted by the members of the consortium in their native language. This page contains nine subsections in the following languages: English, German, French, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Romanian, Polish and Turkish.

It is important to note that the main working and dissemination language for the project is English and it is not the intention of the project to provide all the contents in all the different languages. Each partner will be responsible for providing the basic project information in their local language and to localize the content that is relevant for their country, activity or industry.

3.2 BEACONING PRIVATE SECTION

3.2.1 Private pages

After login into the portal, the Private section can be accessed from the main menu by using the

Beaconing symbol . This section contains the following pages:

- User statistics** – the main role of this page is to provide a statistical classification of the gamified section of the website. This page offers an overview of the points and badges that the users with editing role (authors/editors) have been obtained in the gamified section of the website: Blog, Events and Multilingual. Also this page presents the top 5 blog authors and top events editor of the website;
- Schedules** – this page is accessible only to the members of the Consortium. The objective of this page is to provide information about the deadline on the Beaconing Tasks and Deliverables and also information about upcoming events or meetings;
- Wikis** – this page is accessible only to the members of the Consortium;
- Discussion** – this page is accessible only to the members of the Consortium. The main objective of the page is to facilitate the interaction between the members. In this section the members can add questions or suggestions regarding the Beaconing Project;
- Deliverables** – this page is accessible only to the members of the Consortium. The main objective of this page is to offer a list with all Beaconing deliverables public and private, where the members can download them.

Figure 30. Beaconing Private sections

3.2.2 Registration/ login

To access the private sections of the website and to add articles in the events, blog, brainstorm or multilingual sections members of the consortium must request permission to become an editor/author.

Users can create an account and login using the social network widget from the Top Menu Login: . This widget is connected to an external service and offers the possibility to register or login directly using social network credentials like: Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn.

The website has 3 different defined roles:

- **Administrator:** has full access to the website; can create, edit and delete users' roles; can create, edit and delete articles and comments; can create, edit and delete the contents of all the sections of the website;
- **Author/Editor:** has full access to different sections of the website (Blog, Events, Brainstorm and Multilingual); can create, edit and delete the contents of the articles he/she posted;
- **Subscriber:** can read and post comments in different sections of the website.

3.2.3 Adding an article to a specific section

After a user requested permission to become an editor/author, the user can access the

Dashboard of the website, where the user can access the Blog, Events, Brainstorm, Multilingual, Wikis and Schedules sections and publish articles. A user has the possibility to edit personal articles or to delete them.

Figure 31. Beaconing Back-end editing

4 SOCIAL MEDIA PRESENCE

4.1 TWITTER

The Beaconing Twitter channel was created in December 2015 and its main objective is to promote relevant information. The channel is a useful way to engage participants and increase the impact and the visibility of the project. All the members of the consortium can contribute to this channel.

Figure 32. Beaconing Twitter Channel

The table below presents the main channel indicators used as metrics for social media presence that have been taken into consideration by the Beaconing consortium:

Table 1 - Beaconing Twitter Channel indicators, July 25th 2016

Measured Indicators	
Likes	59
Posts	119
Following	172
Followers	154

4.2 FACEBOOK

The Beaconing Facebook channel was created on April 28th and its main objective is to actively promote the website content, publications, announcements and updates on the project’s progress and other relevant information.

All the members of the consortium can contribute to this channel on a regular basis by posting articles, liking, commenting and above all promoting the page. The main communication language is English.

Figure 33. Beaconing Facebook Channel

The table below presents the channel indicators that have been taken into consideration by the Beaconing consortium:

Table 2 - Beaconing Facebook Channel indicators, July 25th 2016

Measured Indicators	
Likes	208
Page views	294
Posts	65
Countries made aware	31

5 GAMIFICATION

Participation will be actively promoted from the project coordinator and from WP2 leaders, in order to stimulate participation of the Beaconing members within the website, we implemented a gamified interface, where the members can earn points and badges by submitting articles in the website, where certain articles are worth more points than others:

- **Login into the website** – 1 point
- **Posting in the Blog section** - 5 points
- **Posting in the Events section** – 10 points
- **Posting in the Multilingual section** – 20 points

Also, the Beaconing members can earn two types of badges:

- **Posting in the Events section**
- **Posting in the Blog section**

In the private section of the website we implemented a Page with statistics, where the members can see a running history of their total points and badges. Also, we implemented a rank system with the top authors from Blog and Events sections.

Figure 34. Beaconing Statistics Page

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable describes the core guidelines needed to construct a distinctive expression and a consistent visual identity for the Beaconing Project, enabling partners to communicate strategic messages and build strong graphic presentations.

The main outcomes of the activities carried out in Task 2.2 in the first 6 months of the project are the VIG, the development and infrastructure setup of the project website and the dissemination of project activities and outcomes in mainstream social media. These are congruent with the Dissemination and Communication Plan in D2.1.

The project website was created to nurture critical communication processes, and was developed to enable extensive flexibility, allowing individual, creative expression. The website coupled with social media channels provide consistent communication mechanisms both internally, at consortium level, and externally with key targeted audiences.

6.1 RESULTS

Estimated and achieved Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Beaconing online presence are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Beaconing Website online presence, July, 25th 2016

Impact Objective/Month	Estimated	Achieved
Beaconing Portal	1	1
Countries made aware	10	60
No. of Beaconing Portal page hits	500	8993
No. of unique visitors	20	1303
No. of return visitors	10	204
No. of links to Beaconing portal	14	67
No. of video/audio podcasts and tutorials		4
Social media		
No. of posts in social networks	10	Facebook: 65 Twitter: 59
No. of supporters/subscribers	14	Facebook: 208 Twitter: 154

6.2 IMPACT

Consistency of communication to both internal and external audiences achieved through the VIG, the project website and the social media accounts reinforces Beaconing’s impact and sustainability.

Due to the significant and consistent efforts of the Beaconing team, the achieved impact in the first six months of the project lifetime was higher than the initial estimates.

Figure 35. Online presence statistics

APPENDIX I – ONLINE PRESENCE: COUNTRIES MADE AWARE

APPENDIX II – ONLINE PRESENCE: PORTAL PAGE HITS

APPENDIX III – ONLINE PRESENCE: UNIQUE VISITORS

APPENDIX IV – ONLINE PRESENCE: RETURN VISITORS

APPENDIX V – ACCESSIBILITY MARKUP VALIDATION